

Phytochemical informatics: An insight for biological research

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Abstract

Phytochemicals are profoundly used to treat different diseases across the world and have been reported in numerous traditional medicine systems. Phytochemical informatics is composed of various databases, analytical and screening methods used for phytochemical compounds. The phytochemical information stored in databases has various structures which help users to retrieve and analyze large scale data by computational methods. These databases are growing precipitously with the steep expansion of chemical information. Currently, chemical databases have wide applications from novel drug designing, virtual screening, docking, interaction studies to the development of algorithms. These are used for analyzing large scale experimental data and comparison. Chemical databases usually cover all aspects of chemical compounds viz. structure, physicochemical properties, metabolism, reaction, targets, side effects, metabolic pathways in diseases, interactions and reactions. We have compiled the latest phytochemical databases, with their features along with their application for researchers to explore and expand for defining new avenues of phytochemical informatics.

Key Words: Phytochemical informatics, database, chemical structure, drug interaction, metabolism, side effect.

Introduction:

Several historical shreds of evidence in various civilizations represent that humans have an immense understanding of phytochemicals and their applications (Ven Murthy et al., 2010, Shuping et al., 2017, Stojanoski 1999, Bottcher 1965, Wiart 2007, Gorunovic and Lukic, 2001). The Indian and Chinese traditional medicinal systems are also using this understanding and information for the disease's treatment (Tucakov 1971, Wiart 2006). With the advancement of information technology where we can compactly store a sizable amount of information and can mine or analyze this huge information rapidly and can be utilized with modern techniques like artificial intelligence (Zhong et al 2018, Yang et al., 2019). Phytochemical informatics can act as a precursor and may lead to advanced phytochemical studies with the help of new technologies. During the COVID pandemic, different information, finding about diseases and a variety of immune-related resources became the need of the hour for new experiment designs based on existing data and analysis of experiments and results. Enhancement of knowledge-based novel discoveries is the most impactful aspect of these resources. The main objective for the development of these chemical databases is to render structural and physicochemical features of any compound (Miller 2002, Ayers 2012, Irwin et al, 2020). These databases can store micro to macro information for any molecule and are applied widely in drug design applications. By using advanced software features, a comparative analytical graph between two or more chemical molecules with similarities and differences can be generated easily, **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Phytochemical data extraction and processing

The major focus of the authors here is to provide a piece of comprehensive knowledge in the advancement of photochemical information collection, storage and usability. This will certainly be useful for providing a broader perspective to the researcher and make them an out-of-box thinker.

Types Chemical Information:

The chemical information is stored in various computer-readable formats some popular formats are Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry specification (SMILE), Structure Data Format (SDF), Protein Data Bank (PDB), MDL file format (MOL), IUPAC International Chemical Identifier (InChI), SYBYL Line Notation (SLN) etc. These formats provide an opportunity to store the chemical information in databases in a structured manner.

Figure 2: Phytochemical informatics sub-branches where dataset, its representation and analysis provide insights towards novel discoveries.

Database Type:

Phytochemical information can be represented and stored in various ways as represented in **Figure 2**, under which we have collated and segregated them into 5 major categories namely phytochemical, structural, properties, ontology and miscellaneous database.

Tools for phytochemical informatics:

In addition to databases, we have enlisted software and packages that are being widely applied for analysis for phytochemical information. These include structure visualization, analysis, optimization, docking, and downstream analysis of chemical and target interactions.

Table 1: List of phytochemical databases.

S. No.	Database Name and URL	Description	Reference
1.	KEGG (https://www.genome.jp/kegg)	Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) is a repository that contains genomic data, chemical molecular data, and systemic functional data. It also contains Gene catalogs from completely sequenced genomes, of higher-level systemic functions of the cell, organism, and ecosystem.	Kanehisa et al., (2000; 2019; 2021); S Goto et al., (1997)
2.	DrugBank (https://www.drugbank.ca/)	It serves as a pharmaceutical knowledge database & has both bioinformatics and cheminformatics resources as it integrates extensive drug target information with detailed drug data. It is freely accessible & provides data on drugs and drug targets.	David S Wishart et al., (2006); Vivian Law et al., (2014); Craig Knox et al., (2011); David S Wishart et al., (2006)
3.	BRENDA (https://www.brenda-enzymes.org/)	It is an information system that includes one of the world's most extensive enzyme databases. It is an electronic database including molecular and biochemical data on enzymes classified by the IU BMB.	Antje Chang et al., (2021)
4.	IMPPAT (https://cb.imsc.res.in/imppat/home)	IMPPAT database is the largest curated database of Indian Medicinal Plants, Phytochemistry And Therapeutics. It provides Chemical categorization, secondary and tertiary chemical structure, physico-chemical properties, projected ADMET properties, drug-likeness scores, and predicted human target proteins for phytochemicals. Database content can be used further for virtual screening.	Karthikeyan Mohanraj et al., (2018)
5.	PlantPepDB (http://14.139.61.8/PlantPepDB/index.php)	PlantPepDB is a repository of plant peptides with various functions and therapeutic actions that has been curated. It includes 3848 peptide entries from 11 databases and 835 peer-reviewed studies. Peptide Family, Peptide Activity, Sequence Length Range and Plant Classification are all options for searching peptides.	Durdam Das et al., (2020)
6.	Plant Metabolic Pathway Databases (https://plantcyc.org/)	PlantCyc database provides access to information regarding unique metabolic pathways found in over 500 plant species that have been manually curated or reviewed. Data can be manually curated and/or computationally predicted knowledge about enzymes, pathways, and other topics through the Plant metabolic network (PMN).	Pascal Schlöpfer et al., (2017)
7.	Dr. Duke's Phytochemical and Ethnobotanical databases (https://phytochem.nal.usda.gov/phytochem/search)	Dr. Duke's Phytochemical and Ethnobotanical Databases is an online database that contains a list of different species, phytochemicals, biological activity and also ethnobotanical usage. It has also covered a large number of plants along with their chemical profiles. Data present is designed in such a way that supports users for browsing and searching.	Duke, J. A. (2020)
8.	PhytoHub (https://phytohub.eu/)	PhytoHub is a free online database that contains comprehensive information on dietary phytochemicals and their human and animal metabolites. There are around 1,200 polyphenols, terpenoids,	Andreia Bento da Silva et al., (2016)

		alkaloids, and other plant secondary metabolites present in widely consumed foods (>350), as well as >560 human or animal metabolites. PhytoHub's curation by scientists with expertise in various phytochemical families makes it an unique database.	
9.	Phyto Molecular Taste database (https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6141601/)	PhytoMolecularTasteDB is a plant-derived tastants and phyto-molecular taste (PMT) of ayurvedic medicinal herbs. It contains 431 ayurvedic medicinal herbs, 94 EPAs, 223 classes of phytochemicals, and 438 different plant-derived tastants.	Dorin Dragos et al., (2018)
10.	Phyto-mellitus (http://www.bicmlacw.org/bt/)	It is a phyto-chemical database with comprehensive data on traditionally used plants for diabetes treatment along with their chemical constituents. Plant based Antioxidant and free radical scavenging are the main active principles. This has the potential to work as herb-drug interactions may produce pharmacodynamic and/or pharmacokinetic results, further research in diabetes and herbal medicine can improve the work of databases.	Sushil Kumar Middha et al., (2009)
11.	Phytochemica (http://faculty.iiitd.ac.in/~bagle_r/webserver/Phytochemica/)	Phytochemica is an organized collection of phytochemicals from five medicinally important Himalayan plants: Atropa belladonna (ATBE), Catharanthus roseus (CARS), Heliotropium indicum (HEIN), Picrorhiza kurroa (PIKU), and Podophyllum hexandrum (POHX). All mentioned plants are reported to provide immense benefits & therapeutic properties against a variety of diseases.	Shivalika Pathania et al., (2015)

Table 2: List of Structural database

S. No.	Database Name and URL	Description	Reference
1.	KEGG (https://www.genome.jp/kegg/)	Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) is a repository that contains genomic data, chemical molecular data, and systemic functional data. It also contains Gene catalogs from completely sequenced genomes, of higher-level systemic functions of the cell, organism, and ecosystem.	Minoru Kanehisa et al., (2019); (2000) S Goto et al., (1997)
2.	Compendium of Common Pesticide Names (http://www.alanwood.net/pesticides/)	Relevant and important agricultural database for trade, registration and legislation as well as in research publications. Only database or collection of all of ISO-approved standard names of chemical pesticides.	Jackowski et al., (2008); Samuel C. Billings et al., (1963)
3.	MAPS Database (http://www.mapsdatabase.com)	Medicinal plant Activities, Phytochemicals & structural database. It serves as a common portal & also provides a test target on which particular plant is effective with guidance to the original paper.	Usman Ali Ashfaq et al., (2013)
4.	KEGG GLYCAN (https://www.genome.jp/kegg/glycan/)	KEGG GLYCAN is a database for experimentally proved glycan structures, containing all unique structures from CarbBank, structures identified from recent publications, and also structures present in KEGG pathways	Kosuke Hashimoto et al., (2005); (2006); (2009);

			Minoru Kanehisa et al., (2017); Kiyoko F Aoki et al., (2004)
5.	Biological Magnetic Resonance Data Bank (https://bmr.io/)	It contains NMR Spectroscopy structures of Proteins, Peptides, Nucleic Acids, and other Biomolecules. It is a public db and includes nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy data of physiologically significant compounds as well.	Eldon L Ulrich et al., (2008)
6.	PubChem (https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/)	Database collection for Chemicals and their bioassays. It is maintained by NCBI, part of the National Library of Medicine which is part of National Institutes of Health in United States (NIH). PubChem is available for free via a web user interface. PubChem consists of three inter-linked databases, Substance, Compound and BioAssay. Compound database stores unique chemical structures extracted from the Substance database	Sunghwan Kim et al., (2021)

Table 3: List of Software used for chemical analysis

S. No.	Database Name and URL	Description	Reference
1.	ZINC (http://zinc.docking.org/)	Free commercial compiled library of commercially available chemical compounds produced specifically for Virtual Screening. It depicts a biologically relevant, 3-D form of molecule.	Irwin & Shoichet, (2005)
2.	eMolecule (https://www.emolecules.com/)	Platform helps to explore and evaluate uncharted chemical and biological space with a database of over 8 million compounds available from worldwide networks. It serves the purpose of - Drug Discovery programs.	
3.	NMRShiftDB (http://nmrshiftdb.nmr.uni-koeln.de/)	Nmrshiftdb is a freely accessible NMR web database & stores organic structures and their nuclear magnetic resonance (nmr) spectra.	Haiyan Zhang et al., (2003) R. Verpoorte et al., (2007)
4.	STITCH (http://stitch.embl.de/)	STITCH is a database of chemical-protein interactions that is both known and expected. The interactions arise from computing prediction, knowledge transfer across organisms, and interactions gathered from other (main) databases, and they comprise both direct (physical) and indirect (functional) correlations.	Michael Kuhn et al., (2008); (2010); (2012); (2014) Damian Szklarczyk et al., (2016)
5.	KCaM (KEGG Carbohydrate Matcher) (https://www.meta.org/papers/kcam-kegg-carbohydrate-matcher-a-software-tool/15215393)	It is a tool for carbohydrate sugar chains, or glycans analysis. It is a GUI that allows users to enter glycans structures by users then it will be transformed into KCF (KEGG Chemical Function) file format. Further it is sent to a program that implements an efficient tree-structure alignment algorithm, same as sequence alignment algorithms but for branched tree structures.	Kiyoko F. Aoki et al., (2004)

6.	KegTools (https://www.kegg.jp/kegg/download/kegtools.html)	Desktop applications that support Mac OS X, Windows, and Linux platforms with Java 1.6 or newer versions.	Si Zheng et al., (2019)
7.	Biological Magnetic Resonance Data Bank (https://bmr.io/)	Database collection from NMR Spectroscopy on Proteins, Peptides, Nucleic Acids, and other Biomolecules. It is a public db and includes nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy data of physiologically significant compounds as well.	Eldon L. Ulrich et al., (2008)
8.	IMPPAT (https://cb.imsc.res.in/imppat/home)	IMPPAT database is the largest curated database of Indian Medicinal Plants, Phytochemistry And Therapeutics. It provides Chemical categorization, secondary and tertiary chemical structure, physico-chemical properties, projected ADMET properties, drug-likeness scores, and predicted human target proteins for phytochemicals. Database content can be used further for virtual screening.	Karthikeyan Mohanraj et al., (2018)
9.	I-TASSER (https://zhanggroup.org/I-TASSER/)	I-TASSER is a tool package of Zhang lab and used for predicting 3D structure of protein molecules from the given amino acid sequences.	Ambrish Roy et al., (2010); Jianyi Yang et al., (2015)
10.	MOE (https://www.chemcomp.com/Products.htm)	Molecular Operating Environment (MOE) is a wide platform for protein structural modeling, protein families and antibodies	Santiago Vilar et al., (2008)
11.	SBL (https://sbl.inria.fr/)	The Structural Bioinformatics Library: end-user applications and advanced algorithms	Frédéric Cazals et al., (2017)
12.	BALLView (https://ball-project.org/)	3D structural modeling and structure visualization	Andreas Moll et al., (2005); (2006)
13.	STING (https://www.cbi.cnptia.embrapa.br/)	Structural visualization and analysis	G Neshich et al., (2006)
14.	PyMOL(https://pymol.org/2/)	Viewer and modeling	Daniel Seeliger et al., (2010)
15.	VMD (http://www.ks.uiuc.edu/Research/vmd/)	Viewer, molecular dynamics analysis	W Humphrey et al., (1996)
16.	KiNG (http://kinemage.biochem.duke.edu/software/)	An open-source Java kinemage viewer	A Krupa et al., (2004)
17.	STRIDE (http://webclu.bio.wzw.tum.de/stride/)	2D structure prediction from coordinates	Matthias Heinig et al., (2004)
18.	MolProbity (http://molprobity.biochem.duke.edu/)	Structure-validation web server	Christopher J Williams et al., (2018)
19.	PROCHECK (https://web.archive.org/web/20080801065546/http://www.biochem.ucl.ac.uk/~roman/procheck/procheck.html)	A structure-validation web service for proteins and analysis of its conformations.	R A Laskowski et al., (1996)

20.	CheShift (http://cheshift.com/)	On-line application for protein structure-validation	Osvaldo A Martin et al., (2013)
21.	3D-mol.js (https://3dmol.csb.pitt.edu/)	A Javascript based molecular viewer web applications	Nicholas Rego et al.,2015
22.	PROPKA (https://web.archive.org/web/20070113065659/http://propka.ki.ku.dk/)	It is an empirical structure/function relationships based Rapid prediction of protein pKa values	Michał Rostkowski et al., (2011)
23.	Docking Server (https://www.dockingserver.com/web)	Web based molecular docking server	Zsolt Bikadi et al., (2009)
24.	StarBiochem (http://star.mit.edu/biochem/)	A java protein viewer, features direct search of protein data bank	
25.	SPADE (https://sites.google.com/view/spade)	The structural proteomics application development environment	Anton Bankevich et al., (2012) Deacon J. et al., (2008)
26.	PocketSuite – Pocket Depth (http://proline.physics.iisc.ernet.in/pocketdepth/)	A web server for binding site-level analysis. PocketDepth is for Binding site prediction.	Yeturu Kalidas et al., (2008)
27.	PocketSuite – PocketMatch (http://proline.physics.iisc.ernet.in/pocketmatch/)	PocketMatch (Binding site comparison)	Kalidas Yeturu et al., (2008)
28.	PocketSuite – PocketAlign (http://proline.physics.iisc.ernet.in/pocketalign/)	PocketAlign (Binding site alignment)	Kalidas Yeturu et al., (2011)
29.	http://proline.biochem.iisc.ernet.in/PocketDB/	Pocket database consists of 249096 pockets helps in large scale binding site prediction.	Bhagavat Raghu et al., (2018)
30.	MSL (http://msl-libraries.org/index.php?title=Main_Page)	An open-source C++ molecular modeling software library for the implementation of structural analysis, prediction and design methods	Daniel W Kulp et al., (2012)
31.	PSSpred (https://zhanggroup.org/PSSpred/)	Protein secondary structure or 2D structure prediction	Renxiang Yan et al., (2013)
32.	Proteus (http://proteus.dcc.ufmg.br/)	Webtool for mutation pairs suggestions	Barroso J M et al., (2020)
33.	SDM (http://marid.bioc.cam.ac.uk/sdm2)	A server for predicting mutations effects of protein structural stability	Arun Prasad Pandurangan et al., (2017)

Table 4: Chemical Ontology Database

S. No.	Database	Description	Reference
1.	PubChem (https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/)	Database collection for Chemicals and their bioassays. It is maintained by NCBI, part of the National Library of Medicine, which is part of National Institutes of Health in the United States (NIH). PubChem is available for free via a web user interface.	Sunghwan Kim et al., (2021)
2.	ChEMBL (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/chebi/)	ChEMBL is a manually curated bioactive molecules database It combines chemical, bioactivity, and genetic data to help in translation of genomic data into novel drugs.	Janna Hastings et al., (2016)
3.	ChemExper (http://www.chemexper.com/)	ChemExper is a credible and high-quality chemical information database, acknowledged as a chemical directory.	Nikolas Papanikolaou et al., (2016)
4.	ChemMine (http://chemmine.ucr.edu/)	Online service for performing clustering and analyzing chemical or small molecules, for chemical and structural similarity	Tyler W H Backman et al., (2011)
5.	ChemSpider Synthetic Pages (http://cssp.chemspider.com/)	It is a free database contains practical procedures of synthetic chemistry. ChemSpider Synthetic Pages is the only interactive chemistry database.	Antony Williams et al., (2014) Meredith Ayers et al., (2012)
6.	ChemSpider InChI Resolver (http://www.chemspider.com/InChiResolverDecommissioned.aspx)	It is freely available chemical structure database, provides quick access to over 100 million structures, characteristics with other details. It allows researchers to find comprehensive perspective chemical data in a single web search.	Stephen Heller et al., (2013)
7.	Spectral Database for Organic Compounds (https://sdfs.db.aist.go.jp/sdfs/cgi-bin/cre_index.cgi?lang=eng)	Spectral Database for Organic Compounds (SDFS) is a searchable database online freely available. It is hosted by National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology (AIST) in Japan, which has spectral data for around 34,000 organic molecules. It is a compiled spectral database system for organic compounds that contains 6 different types of spectra under a catalog of compounds.	Yamaji, T., et al. (2009)
8.	Electronic Encyclopedia of Reagents for Organic Synthesis (https://www.library.ucdavis.edu/database/encyclopedia-of-reagents-for-organic-synthesis-e-eros/)	It is the Encyclopedia of more than 3,800 reagents for Organic Synthesis.	David Pierrot et al., (2014)
9.	BindingDB (http://bindingdb.org/bind/index.jsp)	BindingDB is a public, web-accessible database of measured binding affinities, also includes interactions of protein considered to be drug-targets with small, drug-like molecules.	Tiqing Liu et al., (2007) Michael K. Gilson et al., (2015)
10.	ChemSpider (http://www.chemspider.com/Default.aspx)	ChemSpider is a free chemical structure database that provides fast text and structure search access to over 100 million structures from hundreds of data sources. chemical names, chemical structure, Literature references, Physical properties, Interactive spectra and Chemical suppliers-based searches are available.	Harry E. Pence et al., (2010)

11.	Chemical Identifier Resolver (https://cactus.nci.nih.gov/chemical/structure)	This helps in the interconversion of the various chemical structure identifiers.	Gert Wohlgenuth et al., (2010) Jon Chambers et al., (2013)
12.	AromaDb (http://bioinfo.cimap.res.in/aromadb/)	Database of Medicinal and Aromatic Plant's Aroma Molecules with Phytochemistry and Therapeutic Potentials	Yogesh Kumar et al., (2018)
13.	Crystallography Open Database (http://www.crystallography.net/cod/)	Organic, inorganic, metal-organic, and mineral compounds and minerals crystal structures are present in this database. It is developed by Nick Day at the University of Cambridge's Department of Chemistry under the supervision of Peter Murray-Russell.	Saulius Gražulis et al., (2009)
14.	Phytochemica (http://faculty.iiitd.ac.in/~bagler/websewers/Phytochemica/)	Phytochemica is an organized collection of phytochemicals from five medicinally important Himalayan plants: Atropa belladonna (ATBE), Catharanthus roseus (CARS), Heliotropium indicum (HEIN), Picrorhiza kurroa (PIKU), and Podophyllum hexandrum (POHX). These plants are reported to provide immense benefits & therapeutic properties against various diseases.	Shivalika Pathania et al., (2015)
15.	Compendium of Common Pesticide Names (http://www.alanwood.net/pesticides/)	It is relevant and important agricultural database for trade, registration and legislation along with research publications. Only database or collection of all of ISO-approved standard names of chemical pesticides.	Jackowski et al., (2008) Samuel C. Billings et al., (1963)
16.	Reaxys (https://www.elsevier.com/en-in/solutions/reaxys)	Reaxys is a chemical database that improves R&D efficiency. Reaxys is used by chemists from all fields to find chemistry literature and bioactivity data.	

Table 5: R and Python packages for small molecule analysis

	Tools	URL	Brief Description	Reference
1.	mol2vec	https://github.com/samoturk/mol2vec.git	Vector representation of Molecular substructure	Jaeger et al., (2018)
2.	PaDEL	http://www.yapcwsoft.com/dd/padeldescriptor/PaDEL-Descriptor.zip	Computational method for 2D and 3D descriptor generation	Yap et al., (2011)
3.	Dragon	http://146.107.217.178/lab/edragon/start.html	Calculation of Molecular descriptor	Todeschini and Consonni, (2009)
4.	ChemDes	http://www.scbdd.com/chemdes	Calculation of Molecular descriptor from various methods including 2D, 3D and fingerprints	Donget al., (2015)
5.	mordred	https://github.com/mordred-descriptor/mordred.git	Python package for molecular descriptor calculations	Moriwaki et al., (2018)
6.	Pybel	https://openbabel.org/docs/dev/UseTheLibrary/Python_Pybel.html	A wrapper on the OpenBabel to develop python script for cheminformatics	O'Boyle et al., (2008)

7.	CDK	https://cdk.github.io/	A cheminformatics toolkit for performing computation of molecular descriptor and manipulation files.	Willighagen et al., (2017)
8.	RDKit	https://github.com/rdkit	2D and 3D molecular descriptor and fingerprint generation for machine learning	Bento et al., (2020)
9.	BlueDesc	http://www.ra.cs.uni-tuebingen.de/mitarb/hinselmann/software/ODDescriptors.jar	Calculates Molecular Descriptor for 3D molecules	Cao et al., (2013)
10.	Chemopy	http://code.google.com/p/pychem/downloads/list	Python package for chemical and small molecule analysis	Cao et al., (2013)
11.	jCompoundMapper	http://jcompoundmapper.sourceforge.net/	Open-source tool for molecular fingerprints generation	Hinselmann et al., (2011)
12.	ChemmineR	https://www.bioconductor.org/packages/devel/bioc/vignettes/ChemmineR/inst/doc/ChemmineR.html	A complete toolkit for small molecule analysis	Cao et al., (2008), Cao et al., (2014)
13.	OpenBabel	http://openbabel.org/wiki/Get_Open_Babel	Python based tool for converting one chemical file format to other	O'Boyle et al., (2011)
14.	KNIME	https://www.knime.com/downloads	Java based tool with various cheminformatics plugins to develop workflows and process for chemical data analysis	Berthold et al., (2009)
15.	rcdk	https://cran.r-project.org/src/contrib/rcdk_3.5.0.tar.gz	Java framework for chemoinformatic analysis which allows descriptor calculation, fingerprint evaluation, and other chemical analysis.	Voicu et al., (2020)
16.	cluster	https://cran.r-project.org/bin/windows/contrib/4.3/cluster_2.1.3.zip	R package to build clusters for chemical compounds with similar properties	Voicu et al., (2020)
17.	chemmodlab	https://github.com/jrash/chemmodlab	R package for fitting and accessing modeling.	Ash and Hughes-Oliver, (2018)
18.	Rcpi	https://www.bioconductor.org/packages/Rcpi	R-Bioconductor package to generate various descriptors of proteins, compounds along with their interactions.	Cao D S et al., (2015)

Table 6: Miscellaneous table

S. No.	Database	Description	Reference
1.	PlantGDB (https://www.plantgdb.org/)	PlantGDB is a unique database of plant molecular sequences of all plant species that is extensively sequenced. The database groups EST sequences into contigs, which actually represents a potential distinct gene. Contigs are annotated and linked to their relevant genomic DNA.	Qunfeng Dong et al., (2004); (2005) Jon Duvick et al., (2008)
2.	Phytozome (https://phytozome.jgi.doe.gov/pz/portal.html)	Phytozome, the Plant Comparative Genomics portal of the Department of Energy's Joint Genome Institute, offers JGI users and the larger plant research community with a central location for accessing, viewing, and analyzing JGI-sequenced plant genomes, as well as selected genomes and datasets sequenced elsewhere. Different tools are used in phytozome for utilization and visualization of data. It also provides evolutionary history study of every plant gene at the level of sequence, gene structure, gene family and genome organization.	David M Goodstein et al., (2012)
3.	Phytome (https://www.hs-ls.pitt.edu/obrc/index.php?page=URL1140550843)	Phytome is a comparative genomics database based on publicly available sequence and map data from a wide range of plant species, with an emphasis on angiosperms. Functional genomics, molecular breeding, and evolutionary studies in model and non-model plant species are all made easier by Phytome.	Stefanie Hartmann et al., (2006)
4.	PlantGDB (https://www.plantgdb.org/)	PlantGDB is a unique database of plant molecular sequences of all plant species that have been subjected to extensive sequencing. The database groups EST sequences into contigs, each of which represents a potential distinct gene. Contigs are annotated and linked to their relevant genomic DNA whenever possible.	Matthew D Wilkerson et al., (2006); Shannon D Schlueter et al., (2005).
5.	BIOPEP database (http://www.uwm.edu.pl/biochemia/index.php/pl/biopep)	BIOPEP is open access resource sensory peptides and amino acids. It also includes tools for finding peptides in protein sequences (potential sensory activity profiles), comparing protein sequences as precursors of sensory peptides by using the frequency of sensory fragments as a quantitative descriptor. It also simulate proteolysis, and calculates novel parameters for quantitative description of simulated proteolysis.	Piotr Minkiewicz et al., (2019) Marta Dziuba et al., (2013); Anna Iwaniak et al., (2016)
6.	Plant DNA C-values Database (https://cvalues.science.kew.org/)	The Plant DNA C-values Database is an extensive catalog of C-value (nuclear DNA content, or in diploids, genome size) data for land plants and algae.	Jaume Pellicer et al., (2019)
7.	Plant rDNA database (https://www.plantrdnadatabase.com/)	The Plant rDNA database is an online resource that provides data regarding the number, position, and structure of ribosomal DNA signals for 2148 plant species (3783 entries). The information was gathered from 785 papers on plant molecular cytogenetics, the majority of which used fluorescent in situ hybridization (FISH) of the 5S and 18S-5.8S-26S ribosomal RNA genes (rDNA)	Sònia Garcia et al., (2012); (2014). Daniel Vitales et al., (2017)
8.	Structural Biology Knowledgebase (http://sbkb.org/)	SBKB is an open web resource designed to turn the results of structural genomics and structural biology attempts into knowledge that the biological community can use to better understand living systems and	M.J. Gabanyi et al., (2011)

		disease. It serves as a common platform that integrates structure, sequence, and functional annotations including technical information regarding protein production and structure determination.	
9.	PISCES	PISCES is a protein sequence culling server for sets of protein sequences from Protein Data Bank (PDB) by sequence identity and structural quality criteria.	Guoli Wang et al., (2003)
10.	TOPOFIT-DB (http://mozart.bio.neu.edu/topofit/index.php)	TOPOFIT-DB, (TDB) is a comprehensive web based collection of protein structural alignments based on the TOPOFIT method, which serves as a detailed resource for comparing protein structure families.	Chesley M Leslin et al., (2007)
11.	Structural Classification of Proteins (https://scop.mrc-lmb.cam.ac.uk/)	The SCOP database, created by manual inspection, provides a detailed and comprehensive description of structural and evolutionary relationships between all proteins whose structure is known. It can be browsed via - Protein type or Protein structural class. It has a manual classification of protein structural domains based on similarities of their structures and amino acid sequences.	Loredana Lo Conte et al., (2000)
12.	Worldwide PDB (http://www.wwpdb.org/)	Protein Data Bank (PDB) has acted as a single repository for knowledge on the three-dimensional structures of proteins, nucleic acids, and complex assemblies. Worldwide PDB (wwPDB) organization is in charge of managing the PDB archive and ensuring that it is freely and publicly accessible to the entire world.	H.M. Berman et al., (2003); (2007) wwPDB consortium et al., (2019)
13.	RCSB PDB (https://www.rcsb.org/)	The RCSB PDB expands on the data by developing tools and resources for molecular biology, structural biology, computational biology, and other fields. RCSB PDB (Research Collaboratory for Structural Bioinformatics PDB) manages the global PDB archive's US data center and makes PDB data freely available to all data users with no restrictions on use.	H M Berman et al., (2000)
14.	Protein Data Bank in Europe (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pdbe/)	PDBe is a European data repository for biological macromolecular structures and founding member of the Worldwide Protein Data Bank that collects, organizes, and disseminates information	Aleksandras Gutmanas et al., (2014)
15.	Electron Microscopy Data Bank (EMDB) (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/emdb/)	The Electron Microscopy Data Bank (EMDB) is a public database that houses volume maps and tomograms of macromolecular complexes and subcellular structures created by electron cryomicroscopy. Single-particle analysis, electron tomography, and electron crystallography are only a few of the techniques covered	Lawson CL et al., (2016)
16.	PDBj (Protein Data Bank Japan) (https://pdbj.org/)	PDBj (Protein Data Bank Japan) is a project team operating under the Joint Usage and Research activities of the Institute for Protein Research, Osaka University	Akira R. Kinjo et al., (2017); (2018)
17.	UGENE (http://ugene.net/)	UGENE is cross-platform, free open-source bioinformatics software that helps in annotations, multiple alignments, phylogenetic trees, NGS assemblies, and others.	Konstantin Okonechnikov et al., (2012) Olga Golosova et al., (2014) Rebecca Rose et al., (2018)

Discussion:

Phytochemicals are natural compounds of diverse functions and their therapeutic potential is well known from ancient times. Globally these chemicals are accepted as plant-based drugs and medicines with least side effects. Various traditional medicines have taken the advantage to treat patients with various ailments. Phyto-informatics as a discipline deal with advanced techniques for computational and information science to store, retrieve and analyze phytochemical constituents. Due to development of high-end computations phytomolecules based information was explored and collected on a large scale from the last few years. In the current article we collated and compiled important phytochemical databases, structural databases along with software used for chemical analysis, chemical ontology database, R and Python packages for small molecule analysis and miscellaneous information for ease of research and as a resource for comprehensive information. The information is represented so that one easily finds resources along with description and links and latest references. This definitely provides a convenient platform for the users or researchers who are working on the field of phytochemical based medicinal botany, phytochemistry, phytochemical based drug designing etc.

Conclusion:

Phytochemical informatics consists of detailed information and analysis of chemical compounds obtained from natural resources. These databases and their information content are growing rapidly, with the addition of new molecules in the system. Each new molecule adds novel insights for biological as well as chemical research. Advancement in computational methods for novel drug designing along with molecular docking defines the complete story of chemical analysis. These computational methods can also provide stability checks to biological activity analysis for the novel area of research. Phytochemical databases are divided into many sections and categories where each one of them plays a vital role. Here we intended to collate and provide a detailed understanding of phytochemical informatics with advanced technologies to the scientific community.

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Authors' contributions:

AS and NS have collated the data SK has formulated the plan and AS and SK wrote the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Conflict of Interest:

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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